

The Unknown Variable X

Evaluating Experiences

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Abstract: Users are dynamic and so is their interaction with products. This results in unique experiences. The consequent design challenge is to consider, appreciate, and integrate qualities of experiences such as motivational and emotional involvement as well as temporal involvement. From a methodological point of view, most existing product evaluation techniques do not suffice to capture the richness of experiences. They capture the interaction as *an objective still* instead of a *subjective film*. This workshop aims to engage participants actively in the critical exploration of the challenges and opportunities of evaluating experiences. The workshop consists of a discussion and interactive group work. The input for the discussion will be based on notes that participants submit before the conference and on theoretical and empirical background information provided by the authors.

Key words: *User experience, evaluation methods, user-centered design, temporality, motivation.*

1. Introduction

Hedonic qualities and emotions as central aspects of the user experience have been receiving increasing attention when it comes to the evaluation of interactive technology [1, 2]. In contrast to the performance oriented concept of usability, user experience provides an extended perspective on the quality of interaction with technology.

Despite the frequent use of the term “user experience” (or the acronym “UX”) in industrial settings, academic discussions on defining UX are still far from being unequivocal. Some argue that UX is a construct separate from usability as it is often handled in industry, while others see it as an addition to usability [3]. A third group [1, 4] views it as an extension of usability, arguing that UX could be integrated in the ISO definition [5] including effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction. A commonly accepted definition still needs to be established. One attempt has recently been made by defining an ISO standard of UX [6], which “officially” documents that UX is being taken seriously and considered to have additional value to the already existing ISO standard of usability [5].

A variety of frameworks and definitions already exist, however, most of them are still relatively limited. Psychologists consider experiences to consist of meaningful reflections on events of interaction [7]. The ongoing reflections are significantly related to a constant evaluation of affective experiences [8]. In the end, theoretical assumptions and experimental findings must also be applicable in real life scenarios. After all, design should not be an end in itself. Rather, products should be used and therefore they need to be accepted by users [9].

Apart from the necessity of a common theoretical understanding, evaluation methods also have to be found. The focus of the proposed workshop is to reflect on practical consequences of this evolving field. Nowadays, usability labs are widespread and people there seem to know what to do and how to do it. What about UX labs? Would someone in a UX lab know what to do and especially *how to do it*? Should those institutions be more appropriately called UX fields, because you cannot bring the experience in a laboratory setting? Or can you? These are some of the issues that we would like to discuss and tackle in the workshop.

2. Challenge 1-2-3

Three challenges of experience evaluation will be addressed: temporal, emotional, and motivational aspects.

2.1. Dynamics

UX is a temporal phenomenon [10]. The first, the fifth, and the eighty-fourth experience are likely to be different from one another. Product appraisal, emotional responses, the user, and even the product itself are influenced by temporal dynamics: According to Karapanos et al. [11], a positive initial interaction experience is typically motivated by hedonic aspects of product use, while repetitive experiences are related to how meaningful a product has become in one’s life. Sense-making is an ongoing and adapting process that supports preservation of experiences [12]. However, when do we set starting and end points of an experience?

The conceptual user experience lifecycle model ContinUE [Continuous User Experience] [13] recognizes the possibility of repeated episodes and thus the possibility of repetitive experiences. The model illustrates sequential phases of a user experience that go beyond the scope of the usage situation (see Figure 1). It should be recognized that all parts of the user-system-context triad evolve over time. Such dynamics enlarge the difficulty of capturing an experience. This raises the questions of whether the information of *one* experience is sufficient, and also of how continuous variables should be measured.

Figure.1 User Experience Lifecycle Model ContinUE [Continuous User Experience]. Considering only “filled” phases illustrates a unique episode, while all phases taken together indicate repetitive episodes.

2.2. Emotional Responses

In contrast to traditional usability studies, UX acknowledges the key role of emotions in human-product interactions [2]. Emotions can be understood as immediate evaluations of a situation with respect to an individual’s personal concern [14]. Therefore, a product can theoretically elicit all kinds of emotions, depending

on user characteristics, context of usage, and familiarity with the product. Moreover, it is assumed that a product can elicit not only one specific emotion, but also various emotions simultaneously [2]. Often it is the product itself that causes an emotion, but with respect to the dynamic nature of user experience, product-relevant emotions may also be elicited before and after product interaction by a change within the user (e.g. by thoughts, expectations, or memories). Under some conditions, the user may even be unaware about the specific cause of an emotion [2]. A commonly accepted view is to understand an emotion as a complex phenomenon consisting of changes in different subsystems [15]. These changes are related to reactions on the following component levels: Cognitive appraisals, subjective feelings, motor expressions, physiological reactions, and behavioral tendencies. A variety of methods can be applied to measure changes on those components, ranging from heart rate, electrodermal activity (EDA), electromyography (EMG), pupil responses, to various kinds of survey methods and behavioral assessments [9]. However, only the combination of methods captures the multidimensional nature of emotions in human-technology interaction [16]. Up to now, economic and valid methods are required that measure ongoing affective evaluations *without interfering* an experience.

2.3. Motivation to Use

Since experiences are preserved on the basis of affective evaluations, these meaningful reflections have a decisive influence on motivation and the direction of users' future actions [17]. Expectancy theory suggests that not only the instrumental value of a successful interaction in combination with a high likelihood of achievement is appealing, but also the outlook of a positive emotional state. The maximization of positive and minimization of negative emotions is a key driver of human behaviour. Technology acceptance and adoption are essential parts of UX: they can be prerequisites as well as consequences of interactions. On the one hand, in addition to perceived usefulness and ease of use, perceived enjoyment has been shown as a valuable predictor of technology adoption [18]. On the other hand, positive emotions experienced while interacting with a system serve as an intrinsic motivator that will prolong and enhance the user-involvement [19]. This kind of motivation "escape[s] measurement in economic terms" [19, p.45] and calls for new forms of assessment. Methodological issues concerning the nature of evaluation methods that capture motivational aspects (passive or active, explicit or implicit, before or after usage) will be discussed in the workshop.

3. Approach

The aim of the workshop is to specifically address the three above-mentioned challenges by discussing, creating, and playing out possible evaluation solutions. The workshop will consist of two parts: During the first part, current challenges and opportunities in the field of UX will be discussed. The discourse will be facilitated by notes participants submit prior to the conference. In the second part, participants will engage in focused group sessions. The task will be a solution-oriented generation of UX evaluation tools that explicitly target the three previously introduced challenges. As UX is always context-dependent, participant groups will work on different context scenarios. This is intended to highlight the differences and commonalities of identified solutions. The settings are chosen from the main conference topics. In a plenary session, the methodological approaches will be presented to the rest of the workshop participants, and the experience and evaluation thereof will be played out. Characters are "the user", "the method", and "a commentator".

The goal of the workshop is an exploration of evaluation techniques that assess experiences in the context of emotions in design. Participants are challenged to reflect on and create solutions for capturing temporal, emotional, and motivational aspects of experiences. Taking a number of context scenarios into account will provide insights into a broader field of applications. The development of solution possibilities will sharpen awareness on the one hand, but at the same time decrease the threshold to evaluate UX in practice later on. A variety of disciplinary backgrounds (design, computer science, psychology, marketing, neuroscience, biology, etc) is welcomed and intended to amplify the exchange of knowledge, ideas, perspectives, and positions.

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